

**THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL
FRAMEWORK FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR
AND YOUTH SPORT COACH EDUCATION AND
TRAINING**

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TECHNICAL SHEET

Title: Theoretical and methodological framework for Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education and Training

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PROJECT PARTNERS

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1. INTRODUCTION

Any educational programme, in this case Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education programmes, needs a framework that it is based on. Therefore, a theoretical and methodological framework is necessary, in order to define a basis to follow for the development of course modules and teaching units. The target groups which will need and use the framework as a basis for the development of R#5, are the following:

- Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education Institutions;
- Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Educators;
- Researchers active in the field of Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education;
- NGO's like research associations, educator and coach associations, etc.;
- Stakeholders and policy makers in charge of Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education.

So far, a general, European-wide useable theoretical and methodological framework for Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education, based on a pre-defined target educator and coach profile, does not exist. As an element of innovation, the developed theoretical and methodological framework allows to develop course modules and micro-modules following the same, common basis. Besides this, the framework can be used by any interested institution offering respective Early Childhood Educator and youth sport coach education and training programmes.

Non-formal and informal physical activity (PA), movement, play, and sport (PAMPS) benefit all in the physical, social, and cognitive domains. Therefore, adequate educational programmes for Early Childhood Educators active in non-formal settings and Youth Sport Coaches active in informal settings in sport clubs (initial education; professional development/in-service education) preparing for the delivery of quality PA, movement, play, and sport are of the highest importance (Bailey et al., 2023; European Commission, 2008; MacPhail et al., 2018).

The EduPASS project partners recognise that one issue for respective curriculum formulation on vocational and higher education levels is what constitutes an Early Childhood Educator and a Youth Sport Coach for PAMPS, the relationship between these roles within different European education systems, and potential connection points. Therefore, an inclusive approach must be taken, and current European-wide practices must be considered.

Thus, the EduPASS project partners are seeking a general approach focusing on the education and training of Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches of PAMPS, allowing an adaptation to national/regional contexts and / or diverse phases of education and training (initial education; professional development/in-service education). Because of the different accreditation practices of well-established and legally constituted national frameworks across Europe, the need for flexibility in delivering educational programmes must be recognised (Bailey et al., 2023).

Early childhood and childhood are crucial periods for motor development, to develop physical literacy and for laying a foundation for lifelong involvement in sport and PA. Promoting PA and motor competence particularly at these developmental stages is highly beneficial for a healthy and active lifestyle (Goodway et al., 2019). One of the key tasks is to provide young children with basic motor competencies (BMC) in order to be physically active and participate in sports, both within physical education (PE) settings and outside school in extracurricular activities (European Commission / EACEA / Eurydice, 2013; SHAPE America, 2014).

Still, broad-spread concern about Early Childhood Educator training programmes, teacher supply and quality embracing insufficiency in numbers and inadequacy of appropriately qualified educators exists, especially in kindergarten and primary schools (early childhood). At the same time inadequate provision and/or uptake of further professional development opportunities represent an important issue (Hardman et al., 2014).

On the other hand, Youth Sport Coaches often do not have extensive formal training or highly structured work environments that would provide clear examples of how they should frame their role. For example, most teachers must complete several years of university-level preparation and have clearly identified performance outcomes. Most youth sport coaches, however, have few concrete role descriptions or performance outcomes for guidance (Gilbert & Trudel, 2004; Resende & Gilbert, 2015).

Hence, the aim of the EduPASS project is to bring together European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and other stakeholders active in non-formal and informal education, to promote their cooperation and state suggestions to qualify EduPASS. Consequently, and to address the gap from a point of view of HEI's, the aim of this intellectual output (R#4) is to provide theoretical and methodological guidelines for a modular study programme for early childhood educators and youth sport coaches active in PAMPS based on the previous findings and recommendations from EduPASS R#1-3.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Youth Sport Coaches (YSC) are expected to develop and use knowledge from a wide array of disciplines including anatomy, pedagogy, physiology, nutrition, and sport psychology. As a result, comprehensive Youth Sport Coach education programmes have been implemented worldwide without agreeing upon format for programmes between countries, or within countries in some cases. The gap between expected competencies and the typical Youth Sport Coach profile has long been considered a major challenge for youth sports (Gilbert & Trudel, 2004; Resende & Gilbert, 2015).

Lindgren (2011; see also figure 1) and Resende & Gilbert (2015) state that good Youth Sport Coaches often share similar qualities. They leave behind patterns, and have many of the following coaching behaviours:

- they know how to make training fun (and why it's important).
- winning is not the priority. Not winning teaches many life lessons and skills, especially if these are experienced from a young age.
- they teach good sportsmanship from an early age. It not only teaches respect in the world of sport, but in life.
- the coach does not play favourites. Prioritising certain children and athletes over others should be an instant red flag.
- a good sports coach at the youth level needs to be very patient.
- they have a positive can-do attitude. They motivate kids to attend practice, push themselves, and face many challenges.
- youth coaching is about inclusion.
- they teach basic skills (for example, life skills such as teamwork, good communication, sportsmanship, and even fundamental physical skills [balance, jumping, running, hopping, etc.] should be taught.
- they effectively communicate with the kids (especially important when coaching young athletes and kids as they have shorter spans of attention. They are more likely to become distracted. And you might need to explain a concept multiple times (visual and auditory) for them to get it.
- they provide equal playing time and opportunities for all their children.
- they support the development of physical literacy (Physical literacy is the motivation, confidence, physical competence, knowledge and understanding that enables a person to value and participate in physical activity throughout life. (Sport Ireland, 2023).

Figure 1: Youth Sport Coach model by Lindgren (2011)

2.2. EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

Habits and patterns of behaviours begin to take shape from an early age. Good habits acquired at in early childhood can last a lifetime. Early Childhood Educators (ECE) shall enable all the children to discover the joy of movement, emotional and social well-being, and good physical and mental health and physical literacy. The children shall be included in activities in which they can engage in PA, play and social interaction and experience motivation and achievement according to their abilities (WHO, 2019). Non-formal PAMPS settings (e.g., Kindergarten, after school programs) shall help the children get to know their bodies and develop an awareness of their own limits and those of others.

By engaging with this learning area, the children shall be enabled to use their bodies to sense, experience, play, learn, and create.

Thus, ECE should help young children:

- to experience well-being, joy, and achievement through a variety of PA, and know their own needs and explore the human body;
- to develop their motor skills, body control, coordination and physical abilities;
- to evaluate and master risky play through physical challenges;
- to feel confident in their own bodies, gain a positive view of themselves and explore their own feelings;
- to set boundaries for their own bodies and respect the limits of others;
- to be proactive and present, support and challenge the children to engage in physical play and acknowledge their achievements;
- to introduce the children to varied and challenging movement environments, sensory experiences, and physical play both indoors and out, within and outside the non-formal setting.
- to develop physical literacy (Physical literacy is the motivation, confidence, physical competence, knowledge and understanding that enables a person to value and participate in physical activity throughout life; Sport Ireland, 2023).

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1. LEARNING THEORIES

The knowledge of learning theories can help us choose activities to achieve learning targets. Nevertheless, it is also conceivable to combine different theories of learning. Objectivist theories consider knowledge to be absolute and corresponding with reality, whereas constructivist theories consider knowledge as shaped to fit with reality. Other approaches to learning theories have classified them in acquisitionist and participationist theories, where learning is understood as the process of acquiring objective knowledge or as the production of knowledge within a learning community, respectively (Campbell et al., 2019, 2020).

The four dominant learning theories are:

3.1.1. BEHAVIOURISM

Three guiding principles are that human behaviour can be understood by objective analysis, that environmental impacts on behaviour can be complex and subtle, and that future behaviour can be formed with reinforcement. Nevertheless, this learning theory did not engage with how the mind influences learning, why people who experience the same teaching do not all learn the same content equally, or why humans do not always respond to stimuli in the same ways. This led to the development of one of the most widely referenced learning theories to date, the constructivism (Campbell, 2020; Fosnot, 2013).

3.1.2. CONSTRUCTIVISM

The fundamental statement in constructivism is that learners build new knowledge based on previous learning. Interaction with more conversant teachers or peers shape learners' perceptions, which in turn forms knowledge construction. The teacher is a 'director' of knowledge construction rather than the knowledge-giver. Constructivist teaching methodologies include active learning, learning-by-doing, scaffolded learning, creating cognitive conflict or by using reflective writing, and externalising memory on lists and concept maps to stimulate relationships and content over recall. Current sociocultural theories of learning have emphasized the development of student identity as a vital part of the learning process and accounted for the influence of the environment as well as other people. Interactions with others are the foundation in theories such as the theory of communities of practice (Campbell et al., 2019).

3.1.3. COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE

This theory of social learning is founded on observations of apprenticeship learning. It guides education developers to consider the activity, culture and context in which learning takes place. A community of practice forms when group members linked by a concern for an activity learn to perform the activity better through regular interactions. Through observations, apprenticeships, and legitimate peripheral participation (LPP) newcomers can become core participants, recognized by the community as experts (Lave & Wenger, 1991, Wenger, 1998). Knowledge needs a realistic context, and a structure recommends the use of activities such as site visits, guest lecturers and real-life data statistics. Participants gain social capital as they gain knowledge and acknowledgment from their peers. Peer coaching, presenting examples of students' work and guided peer assessment are activities that place students in more central roles in the community of practice (Campbell, 2020; Campbell, Wenner, & Brandon et al., 2022).

3.1.4. CONNECTIVISM

Connectivist-learning is the construction and use of networks of connections between human and non-human information resources or 'nodes' at three levels: the cognitive, concept, and social. Activities include accessing, critically evaluating and synthesizing diverse information resources, and contributing self-generated content through blogs, videos and comments.

3.1.5. INTEGRATION OF LEARNING THEORIES

The panorama of theories on teaching and learning is enormous and dynamic. In a single day, a student may engage with behaviourism-inspired videos with mastery quizzes, connect on social media to a community of practice for advice on solving a homework question, use responses to help their construction of understanding of a topic, and post a social media comment where they share their understanding and the resources that helped them. Whatever learning theories guide the design of the learning activities, early childhood educators and Youth Sport Coaches have the power to influence development or fixed mindsets through their instructional design, whether or not they intend to do so (Campbell, 2020).

Evidence shows that educational programmes are more effective at achieving the missions when they are field- based. Hence, they provide the learners with opportunities to practice skills learned through on-campus methods courses in an authentic setting. Efficient programmes balance field-based learning experiences with on-campus opportunities for continued learning and reflection through constructivist-oriented learning strategies that promote reflection and critical thinking (Campbell et al., 2019).

The theoretical framework for the EduPASS study programme is built on a variety of learning theories which guided the design of the learning activities. Learning theories do not provide “the truth” about learning but provide understanding of how learning happens. Similar to how an understanding of diverse sports may be useful for us to choose what to play to achieve fitness goals, a knowledge of learning theories can help us choose learning activities to accomplish learning goals. It is conceivable to use diverse theories of learning in combination (Campbell, 2019).

Figure 2 presents a structure for EduPASS model which will guide us through the process of providing its specific elements.

Figure 2: *EduPASS Model* (Source: Prepared by the authors)

The mission of the EduPASS project is to prepare programme information for Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches, so as to equip them for a successful future where they build communities of competent and knowledgeable children on their physical literacy journey who value an active and healthy lifestyle and pursue PA. They should be seen as competent professionals who are concerned to become more effective in assisting and enabling children’s physical, social and cognitive learning and development within a variety of contexts through analysing, exploring and reflecting upon their practice

4. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Any programme should be based on a well-adjusted combination of theoretical, practical and professional work across the period of the programme. It should embrace practical activities, educational and teaching sciences, natural and biological sciences, social sciences/humanities, scientific work, and field-based practice, all using **Universal Design for Learning (UDL) as a methodological framework for the design of courses**. All these elements (modules) can be organized into themes to provide a structure for programmes. Personal health and well-being as well as effective communication should not be neglected.

Universal Design for Learning in Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach programmes:

- Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is a framework that guides the design of courses and learning environments to appeal to the largest number of students/learners. It underlines flexibility in how instructional material is presented, how learners demonstrate their knowledge and skills, and in how they are engaged in learning (La et al., 2018). The goal is to use a diversity of teaching methods to eliminate any barriers to learning. From the beginning of the module, it helps to anticipate and to plan for *all* learners, making sure that the greatest range of students can access and engage in learning. The fundamental goal of UDL is for all students to become expert learners. Expert learners are purposeful and motivated, resourceful, and well-informed, and strategic and goal-directed about learning.
- UDL’s principles of multiple means of engagement, representation, and action and expression (see tables 3, 4 and 5) offer educators in Early Childhood Education and Youth Sport Coach Educators an instructional design model to struggle for equitable access for all by offering options and sets goals to accommodate diverse learners. In addition, UDL encourages how to improve their own teaching practice by considering diversity in the classroom, student voice and intervention.
- In order to reduce the lack of training in addressing the needs of diverse learners, educators should consider ways to insert the principles of UDL into their classes / modules (Liebermann & Grenier, 2019).

Table 1: *Suggested methodologies for implementing multiple means of engagement* (adapted from La et al., 2018)

Multiple Means of Engagement	Methodology for classes / modules
Variety in teaching and learning activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combine discussions and small group activities • Insert engagement materials in lecture notes (I.e. sample exam questions). • Plenary lectures • Gamification • Practical seminars • Learning through research
Interaction with others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online and in-class discussions • Problem-based learning • Cooperative learning • Inquiry-based learning • Study groups and teacher assistants
Use of Information and communication technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online learning environment for small group work, discussions, etc. • Flipped classroom
Student choice of course content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One optional unit or topic after standard units have been addressed • Each group researches and presents on a different topic
Self-regulation and motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal setting • Rubrics for self-assessment • Checklists to track progress • Online quizzes for immediate student feedback

Table 2: *Suggested methodologies for implementing multiple means of representation* (adapted from La et al., 2018)

Multiple Means of Representation	Methodology for classes / modules
Accessible course materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Links to Creative Commons resources • Open Education Resources (OER) • Slides, readings, and course materials are published online in advance
Multimodal sources of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Record lectures (if allowed) • Provide models and graphics • Use animations
Pedagogical approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variety of pedagogical approaches (i.e. logic, statistics, narrative, case study, multiple perspective, and testimonial)
Student-created materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphic organizer summary • Concept maps, illustrations, etc. • Class notes posted by students to course site (small groups) • Glossary of terms created by students
Comprehension and key concepts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study guide: list of key concepts at the beginning of each class / module • Practical classes and possible solutions • Highlight patterns and themes between ideas • FAQs and responses online
Check for understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online discussion forums • Q & A session in class • One-minute papers

Table 3: *Suggested methodologies for implementing means of action and expression* (adapted from La et al., 2018)

Multiple Means of Action and Expression	Methodology for classes / modules
Assessment / Exams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple choice, short answer, fill in the blank, equations, label a diagram, etc. • Questions assessing different ways of understanding: remember / comprehend, analyze / apply, and evaluate / create • Add graphics into some questions
Assignments and demonstration of skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Class presentations • Role-play, debate, discussions, reflective diaries, • Develop skills in real PA settings (i.e., teaching practices, peer-teaching, placements)
Feedback for theory and practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-class peer feedback • Use rubrics (observations from different points of view) • Student-led study groups • Cumulative assignments with feedback at different stages • Tutorials
Student choice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due date or topic • Assignment format: paper, presentation, website, poster, reflective diary, etc. • Social media as a communication tool
Assessment anxiety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assignment guidelines to outline your expectations • Provide templates or outlines if appropriate • Option to write final exam as a take-home exam if appropriate • Give sample assignments showing feedback and how they were graded if appropriate

5. COMPETENCE MODEL

EduPASS focusses on the fundamental competences underlying non-formal and informal PAMPS. The 2005 OECD 'DeSeCo' (Definition and Selection of Competences) model which categorised competences in four categories was adopted in EduPASS Project Delphi Study (see also Final Report EduPASS Delphi Study, Bailey et al., 2023):

KNOWLEDGE (K): theoretical concepts and ideas, in addition to practical frameworks based on the experience of having performed in the relevant settings.

SKILLS (S): the abilities and capacities to carry out processes and be able to use one's knowledge in a responsible way to achieve a goal.

ATTITUDES (A): learned tendencies or readiness to evaluate things or react to some ideas, people, or situations in specific ways, either consciously or unconsciously. Attitudes are underpinned by values and beliefs and influence behaviour.

VALUES (V): principles and core beliefs shared by individuals and groups that guide and motivate attitudes, choices, and behaviour and serve as broad guidelines for social life.

EduPASS ranked the competences after 3 rounds of Delphi Study. The objective was to integrate a comprehensive range of competences. Data were gathered in the two settings (non-formal and informal) (See table 4). The **highlighted competencies** represent the five most highly ranked items. Similarities are also shown by inserting connecting arrows. The other competences (below TOP 5) from the Delphi Study are listed in each category, allowing for adaptation to national/regional contexts and / or diverse phases of education and training for early childhood educators and Youth Sport Coaches.

Table 4: Final ranking of competences and similarities after 3rd round of EduPASS Delphi Study

	NON-FORMAL SETTING (i.e. Early Childhood Educator)	INFORMAL SETTING (i.e. Youth Sport Coach)
KNOWLEDGE	Motivation (8.65) Participants' needs (8.43) Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) Child development (8.17) Understanding individual differences (8.13) Youth development (8.0) Behaviour management (7.96) Creativity & problem-solving skills (7.83)	Child's interests & preferences (7.87) Knowledge of basic motor development (7.83) Group Dynamics & Social Interaction (7.74) Learner-centred approaches (7.52) Basic pedagogical knowledge (7.43) The role of play & exploration (7.39) Knowledge of activities in informal PAMPS (7.3) Health & safety processes (7.26)
SKILLS	Communication skills (8.7) Providing a positive learning environment (8.57) Conflict resolution (8.43) Motivating young people (8.39) Listening (8.09) Observation skills (8.22) Organisational skills (8.13) Differentiating for different skill levels (8.04)	Communication skills (8.3) Promoting fun and enjoyment (8.3) Conflict management skills (8.09) Cooperation skills (8.04) Teaching / pedagogical skills (8.01) Motivation (7.91) Leadership skills (7.78) Active Listening (7.74)
ATTITUDES	Positive attitude (8.61) Motivation (8.52) Respect (8.48) Empathy (8.35) Valuing individual differences (8.3) Cooperation (8.3) Professional ethics (8.22) Responsibility (8.22)	Respecting children's needs and interests (8.39) Enthusiasm (8.35) Cooperation (8.26) Motivating (8.26) Creativity (8.3) Fun and enjoyment (8.04) Empathy (8.0) Patience (8.0)
VALUES	Fair play (8.43) Ethical Practice (8.35) Respect (8.22) Inclusion (8.17) Responsibility (8.17) Safety and Well-being (8.09) Equality (8.0) Positive Relationships (8.0)	Ethical behaviour (8.3) Respect (8.26) Fair play (8.22) Cooperation (8.22) Empathy (7.96) Inclusion (7.96) Honesty (7.91) Fun & Enjoyment (7.87)

As is evident from the findings, there is some similarity between the two sets of findings which presents the possibility of inter-setting collaboration and sharing.

6. MODULAR STUDY PROGRAMME

Over the last two decades, the modular structures have been progressively employed in higher education in an attempt to satisfy the needs of more diverse learner groups and to allow them greater flexibility and choice in managing their studies (Dejene & Chen, 2019; French, 2015). The modular approach moves conventional instruction methods to an outcome-based learning paradigm and divides the study programme into independent, non-consecutive, short and small modules or units. It mainly refers to the disaggregation of the content of the programme rather than to a temporal metric (content-based division vs. time-based division) that splits the academic year into two teaching periods or semesters (French, 2015) and stands in contrast to the notion of the traditional university 'subject'. Accordingly, students collect credit for modules which can lead to a qualification for which a stipulated number of credit points is requisite (Dejene & Chen, 2019).

Modular degrees offer several benefits to the students such as flexibility, choice, access and mobility. It is also agreed that modular structures allow HEIs or other educational institutions to better react to the needs of employers, develop more efficient uses of resources and increase opportunities for curricula extensiveness although interdisciplinarity is frequently considered as a positive attribute of modular programmes, yet for some it is also a source of concern (Adesope & Ahiakwo, 2016, French, 2015). Furthermore, it is discussed that modularisation generates the possibility of fragmentation and incoherence of the educational experience, possibly reduces learning outcomes, and arises epistemological, structural and pedagogical challenges. Hence, the modular approach implies teaching and assessing detached components of learning, sometimes excluding more integrative learning outcomes. Somehow, increased accent on learning facilitation and outcomes may come at the expense of a high-quality education (Dejene & Chen, 2019; French, 2015).

However, research reveals that learners prefer modularised and/or intensive course structures as they are perceived to offer more flexibility and freedom of choice. A wide range of motivational factors determine learners' choices (Hedges et al., 2014). Whereas some may be driven by learning and career aspirations, other may choose modules that are perceived to be easier, select modules that are held at a more suitable day and time or to avoid particular modes of assessment. Thus, it is imperative to fulfil the possible benefits of modularisation, that students receive formal guidance during the decision-making process (Hedges, 2014, p. 40).

Modules should combine experience in a range of activities with a detailed intellectual foundation. Thus, the learner or student should be required to develop techniques of analysing, observing, diagnosing, selecting, reporting, and presenting information. These techniques can then be used to test the value of scientific, pedagogical and didactical concepts as well as principles pertinent to the PE/PA study programmes (French, 2015).

6.1. MODULE DESIGN

A modular programme for both Youth Sport Coaches and Early Childhood Educators education consisting of course modules based on the theoretical and methodological framework (R 4) will be developed. A respective programme allows interested higher education institutions, and Youth Sport Coaches and Early Childhood Educators training institutions to choose appropriate modules for their flexible use and implementation. The following template has been designed for this purpose.

Core Module	Title of the core module
Module Number	X
Core Module Aim	The aim of the core module is to achieve:
Module Description	
Module Duration	At least XX hours (maximum XX hours, including XX hours of Self-Directed Learning)
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	<p>Class based lectures / workshops to consider the knowledge / theories pertaining to inclusive coaching and safeguarding.</p> <p>The module will be including field-based practical sessions during which coaches will be involved in experiencing practical coaching skills (peer-coaching), to examine the practical implications and application of the knowledge / theories, when coaching children.</p> <p>Self-directed learning as well as the completion and presentation of case studies will also be part of the module.</p>
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book
Essential Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ...
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for
Module structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 1: Title <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ XX h Lecture Teaching Units ○ XX h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ XX h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2: Title <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ XX h Lecture Teaching Units ○ XX h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ XX h Self-Directed Working hours

Learning outcomes <i>for Youth Sport Coaches</i>	The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they coach:	
	Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
	Attitudes: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they coach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Values: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they coach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i>	The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to support the children they coach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):	
	Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
	Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Connection to other Core Module Course Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	

6.2. COURSE DESIGN

The courses included in each module will use the following structure and template for their design.

Course Title	XX		
Course Number	XX		
Course Description / Main Objective	The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	XX h	Teaching Unit 1:
	W / PE	XX h	Teaching Unit 2:
	L / W	XX h	Teaching Unit 3:
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	•	
	TU 2	•	
	TU 3	•	

7. CORE MODULES

The organisation of the elements of study programmes into themes provides a means of highlighting key aspects for teaching. These core themes are represented for both Youth Sport Coaches and Early Childhood Educators in figures 3 and 4 respectively.

Figure 3: Core modules for Youth Sport Coaches

The following table (Table 5) includes the main and second competency areas for Youth Sport Coaches related to the core modules which were created based on the assessment of the content of the Learning Teaching and Training event (LTT #2 - #3) in Dublin (Ireland).

Table 5: Connections of the core modules with the categories of competences for Youth Sport Coaches

Core module	Informal setting	
	Main competency area	Second competency area
Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	K: Child's interests & preferences (7.87) S: Promoting fun and enjoyment (8.3) A: Enthusiasm (8.35) V: Cooperation (8.22)	K: Knowledge of basic motor development (7.83) S: Communication skills (8.3) A: Creativity (8.3) V: Empathy (7.96)
Principles of Coaching Children	K: Child development (8.17) S: Promoting fun and enjoyment (8.3) A: Respecting children's needs and interests (8.39) V: Ethical behaviour (8.3)	K: Group Dynamics & Social Interaction (7.74) S: Communication skills (8.3) A: Motivating (8.26) V: Respect (8.26)
Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding	K: Child's interests & preferences (7.87) S: Communication skills (8.3) A: Respecting children's needs and interests (8.39) V: Respect (8.26)	K: Learner-centred approaches (7.52) S: Cooperation skills (8.04) A: Cooperation (8.26) V: Empathy (7.96)
Fundamental Movement Skills and Play	K: Knowledge of basic motor development (7.83) S: Teaching / pedagogical skills (8.01) A: Motivating (8.26) V: Fair play (8.22)	K: Basic pedagogical knowledge (7.43) S: Cooperation skills (8.04) A: Creativity (8.3) V: Cooperation (8.22)
Hands-on Coaching	K: Basic pedagogical knowledge (7.43) S: Promoting fun and enjoyment (8.3) A: Enthusiasm (8.35) V: Fair play (8.22)	K: Learner-centred approaches (7.52) S: Teaching / pedagogical skills (8.01) A: Respecting children's needs and interests (8.39) V: Empathy (7.96)
Plan, Reflect and Learn	K: Knowledge of activities in informal PAMPS (7.3) S: Coaching / pedagogical skills (8.01) A: Creativity (8.3) V: Ethical behaviour (8.3)	K: The role of play & exploration (7.39) S: Communication skills (8.3) A: Motivating (8.26) V: Fair play (8.22)

Figure 4: Core modules for Early Childhood Educators

The next table (Table 6) displays the main and second competency areas for Early Childhood Educators related to the core modules which were created based on the assessment of the content of the Learning Teaching and Training event (LTT #4 - #5) in Luxembourg.

Table 6: Connections of the core modules with the categories of competences for Early Childhood Educator

Core module	Non-formal setting	
	Main competency area	Second competency area
Daily Physical Activity & Play	K: Motivation (8.65) S: Communication skills (8.7) A: Positive attitude (8.61) V: Respect & Inclusion (8.22 & 8.17)	K: Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) S: Motivating young people (8.39) A: Motivation (8.52) V: Responsibility (8.17)
Principles of Educating Children	K: Participants' needs (8.43) S: Communication skills (8.7) A: Motivation (8.65) V: Fair play (8.43)	K: Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) S: Providing a positive learning environment (8.43) A: Positive attitude (8.61) V: Ethical practice (8.35)
Inclusive Teaching	K: Participants' needs (8.43) S: Providing a positive learning environment (8.57) A: Empathy (8.35) V: Inclusion (8.17)	K: Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) S: Organizational skills (8.13) A: Positive attitude (8.61) V: Respect (8.22)
Fundamental Movement Skills & Play and Motor Skill Assessment	K: Child development (8.17) S: Communication skills (8.7) A: Motivation (8.52) V: Fair play (8.43)	K: Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) S: Providing a positive learning environment (8.43) A: Positive attitude (8.61) V: Ethical practice (8.35)
Hands-on Teaching	K: Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) S: Communication skills (8.7) A: Empathy (8.35)	K: Participants' needs (8.43) S: Organisational skills (8.13) A: Positive attitude (8.61)

	V: Respect (8.48)	V: Cooperation (community engagement) (8.0)
Plan, Reflect and Learn	K: Participants' needs (8.43) S: Providing a positive learning Environment (8.57) A: Positive attitude (8.61) V: Respect (8.22)	K: Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) S: Communication skills (8.7) A: Motivation (8.52) V: Responsibility (8.17)

Source: designed by the authors

8. COACHING AND TEACHING COMPETENCES RELATED TO THE SIX CORE MODULES

Competences of teachers and learners according the EduPASS Delphi-Study has been identified as four different sectors of competences: knowledge, skills, attitudes and values (KSAV). All six core modules for Youth Sport Coaches and Early Childhood Educators are related to these four sectors of competence, often with cross-competences in each of the six core modules (e.g. knowledge & skills; attitudes & values; knowledge & attitudes & values; skills & attitudes & values). There is no ranking of importance of the four sectors of competences and each core module may be selected for teaching and learning independently form each other according the kind of group and pre-level of development of members of the group/class. However, a certain pathway of process to teach and to learn inside the set of the six core modules may support the total outcome of teaching and learning step by step, module to module for Youth Sport Coaches as well as for Early Childhood Educators.

8.1 YOUTH SPORT COACHES

The European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) has taken this perspective of consecutive teaching and learning by definitions of six functions for the development of a Youth Sport Coach. The set of primary functions of the coach have been collected form consultation of coaches and literature review. The six functions, as outlined in the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017, p. 29-30) are (quoted verbatim in italics):

1. **Set the vision and strategy.** *The coach, in partnership with athletes and teams, creates a vision and a strategy based on the needs and stage of development of the athletes and the organisational and social context of the programme. The coach develops a specific plan that outlines the steps required to bring the strategy to life and realise the vision.*
2. **Shape the environment.** *The coach works with a group of athletes and takes responsibility for the individual objectives and the institution's goals. In order to do so, the coach seeks to optimise the environment in which the programme occurs through the procurement and maximisation of personnel, facilities, resources and working practices and through the management of other coaches and support personnel.*
3. **Build relationships.** *The coach builds positive and effective relationships additional and relevant internal and external competitive opportunities as appropriate to promote individual and team development.*

4. **Conduct practices and prepare and manage competitions.** *The coach organises suitable and challenging practices using effective pedagogy and methodology to promote learning and improvement. The coach prepares for targeted and appropriate competitions and also oversees and manages the athletes in these competitions. The coach creates additional and relevant internal and external competitive opportunities as appropriate to promote individual and team development.*
5. **Read and react to the field.** *The coach observes and responds to events appropriately, including all on-field and off-field matters. Effective decision making is essential to fulfil this function and is a capability that should be developed in all coaches at each stage of their development.*
6. **Reflect and learn.** *The coach evaluates the programme as a whole, as well as each practice and competition, and is continually seeking improvements. In addition, personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the coach's efforts to support the education and development of other coaches.*

Figure 5: Primary functions of the Youth Sport Coach

The primary functions (see Figure 5) are interrelated and interdependent, and they occur within a cyclical process of continuous improvement that includes planning, implementation, review and adjustment.

These primary functions describe how coaches accomplish their aims in general terms. Substantial variation may exist depending on the nature of specific coaching roles and circumstances.

Experienced coaches typically are more engaged in all of the functions than are early-stage coaches. However, with athletes and others associated with the programme. This includes personnel at the club, school, federation and other levels. The coach is responsible for engaging in, contributing to and influencing the organisational context through the creation of respectful and effective working relationships with those he is accountable to (e.g., performance managers, board of directors).

8.2 EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

The example of the European Sport Coaching Framework with the perspective of consecutive teaching and learning by definitions of six functions was adopted to reflect the aims and tasks of Early Childhood Educators in a different but comparable way. Accordingly, six major functions were identified with reference to the outcome of studies and reviews in R 1, R 2 and R 3 of the EduPASS-project. These six aims and tasks to do are:

1. **Vision of holistic education with child-centred actions.** Related competences and content areas to teach and to learn are a part of the module “Principles of educating children”
2. **Shape the infrastructure of the setting.** Items to shape and actions to do are embedded in the module “Fundamental Movement Skills & Play”.
3. **Building partnerships between staff members and relationships to parents and with all children. From the perspective of adopting an inclusive, systemic approach to early childhood education related to the module Inclusive Teaching.**
4. **Provide FMS and Play and support needs of individuals.** There are two modules (“Daily Physical Activity & Play” and “Inclusive Teaching”) which provides the essential competences to offer, to arrange, to support and to motivate children for daily physical activity.
5. **Improve your own learning.** The relevant and corresponding module are “Plan, Reflect & Learn”
6. **Monitor and evaluate children`s outcomes.** Individual feedback about the development of children is needed. The module “Hands-on Teaching” gives information how to do it and what needs to be considered.

Figure 6: Essential aims & tasks of the ECE

9. CONCLUSIONS

EduPASS Project has presented so far, a formalization of a revised profile for Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches that is theory-grounded and outlines key competences and elements detected in a EduPASS R#1 Delphi study undertaken by experts from all over Europe.

Suggestions have been made on teaching methodologies for EduPASS Programmes and the development of the course modules and teaching units for R#5. The assessment of the different modules and teaching units will follow in R#6.

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